

Pedagogical Leadership: A gateway Towards Achieving Quality in Early Childhood Education and Care in South Africa

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Abstract

This study investigated stakeholders' perspectives on pedagogical leadership in Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) and its relationship with quality practices. Stakeholders included ECCE principals, teachers, district officials, and directors, selected through random sampling. The research examined how pedagogical leadership fosters quality practices and contributes to addressing gaps in leadership related studies within ECCE. Given the global prioritisation of quality ECCE, the study focused on identifying leadership approaches that enhance practices in the sector. This qualitative research employed an ontology based constructive paradigm to achieve its objectives, exploring the effects of pedagogical leadership on quality practices within ECCE. Conducted in Gauteng Province, South Africa, data were collected through virtual interviews and a review of relevant literature. Data analysis was facilitated using ATLAS.ti software to interpret participants' perspectives. The findings indicated that pedagogical leadership is essential for ensuring quality practices, including effective communication with stakeholders, curriculum implementation, enhanced teaching, and improved educational outcomes. The study recommends revising ECCE policies to incorporate leadership performance standards that ensure quality education and best practices.

Keywords: pedagogical leadership; quality practices; early childhood education; care; stakeholders; township; multicultural

Introduction

Since the establishment of a democratic government in South Africa in 1994, the early childhood sector has undergone significant advancements. Efforts to enhance Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) have focused on expanding access for all South African children while promoting their holistic development. The ECCE sector has witnessed notable historical changes, marked by the implementation of numerous policies aimed at improving educational outcomes.

Under President Ramaphosa's government-in South Africa, an important policy shift was introduced requiring one year of study before entering Grade R,

resulting in two years of pre-formal education (Department of Basic Education [DBE], Function Shift, 2022). This adjustment reflects the government's commitment to enhancing learner preparedness for formal schooling and raising the quality of early education.

Key legislative frameworks, including the 2015 National Integrated Plan and the National Curriculum Framework, strengthen ECCE operations in South Africa. These policies establish standards and expectations to ensure a consistent and comprehensive approach to early childhood education. In April 2022, a significant administrative change transferred ECCE oversight from the Department of Social Development to the Department of Basic Education (DBE, 2022, p. 3). This transition aimed at improving the quality of ECCE practices, acknowledging the critical role of effective leadership in achieving this objective.

Pedagogical Leadership and ECCE

Pedagogical leadership emphasises the strategic and practical implementation of curricula to meet benchmark standards, focusing on teaching and learning support (Nuñez, 2021). Scholars such as Sarimsakova (2024) argue that pedagogical leadership enables teachers to employ diverse instructional strategies, improving classroom engagement and outcomes. Investing in high-quality personnel, resources, and infrastructure during the ECCE stage is crucial for ensuring school readiness (Hanno et al., 2021). High quality ECCE standards have been shown to enhance children's mental health, reduce developmental risks, and improve academic performance (Wilhelmsen, 2022).

Quality in ECCE is often ambiguously defined, operating within a grey area (Singh et al., 2023). However, the Education Quality (EdQual) Research Consortium identifies recurring dimensions of quality in education, including learners' wellbeing, readiness, support systems, safety, resources, relevant curricula, effective teaching practices, and holistic development (Kyriakides et al., 2020).

Poor quality ECCE can have detrimental effects on children's development, particularly for those from disadvantaged backgrounds (Smith et al., 2022). Effective leadership is pivotal in guiding organisations towards achieving their vision and delivering quality education (Jones & Brown, 2023). In ECCE settings, leadership is often credited for institutional success and criticised when issues arise.

Research Context

This study involved ECCE experts from two open distance learning universities collaborating with ECCE centres to collect data from stakeholders, including the Department of Education, teachers, and principals. Pedagogical leadership encompasses various dimensions, including professional development, governance, accountability, and leadership identity (Strehmel et al., 2020). Quality practices in ECCE classrooms positively impact children's cognitive, motor, and social emotional development (Eurostat, 2014; Kamiya & Nomura, 2022). School ready children are less likely to drop out or repeat grades, contrasting with findings that many children in South Africa enter formal schooling unprepared (Ngololo et al., 2022; Shaw, 2022).

Despite these insights, significant gaps remain in understanding the influence of pedagogical leadership on quality in South African ECCE settings. While Sarimsakova (2024) highlights the importance of leadership in fostering quality and holistic development, there is limited clarity regarding its practical implementation and measurable impact (Hanno, Davids & Samuels, 2021; Wilhelmsen, 2022). Furthermore, Heckman (2021) reports that 55% of children in South African ECCE programmes are underprepared for formal schooling due to various developmental deficits, featuring the urgent need for effective leadership interventions.

Literature Review

Three principal concepts support this study, that is leadership, pedagogy, and quality. Institutional leadership profoundly influences behaviours and decisions that shape organisational outcomes. The global recognition of the role of pedagogical leadership in enhancing the quality of Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) highlights its essential contribution to fostering sustainable teaching and learning practices. Such practices enable teachers to critically reflect on and refine their teaching methodologies (Harris, 2020a). According to Smith and Johnson (2023), the adoption of creative and learner centred approaches is crucial in improving the effectiveness of educational practices, necessitating active listening to learners and providing appropriate guidance. Scholars such as Fullan (2021), Hargreaves (2019), and Senge (2018) emphasise that effective educational leadership involves implementing appropriate strategies to ensure successful curriculum delivery and adherence to best practices.

The innovative framework of transformational leadership, as outlined by Bass (1980), complements pedagogical leadership by encouraging commitment to the

organisation's vision and objectives. Harsoyo (2022) explains that transformational leadership motivates and inspires teachers to achieve positive outcomes and bring about organisational improvements. Similarly, Nyenty (2023) argues that maintaining an effective foundation for transformation necessitates sustained leadership and professional development.

Pedagogical leadership plays a critical role in fostering enhanced teaching and learning through the elevation of curriculum standards and implementation (Ahn et al., 2021). Such leadership may be demonstrated by teachers who cultivate strong relationships with learners or by ECCE directors who ensure the provision of high-quality education. Leadership in ECCE centres is thus indispensable for delivering quality instruction and creating optimal educational opportunities for young children (Douglass, 2019). Furthermore, it cultivates key competencies such as self-assurance, problem-solving abilities, and collaborative skills among teachers and learners alike (Smith, 2018; Johnson, 2019; Brown, 2020). Leadership in this context encompasses efforts to develop, support, and inspire ECCE practitioners, enabling them to provide exemplary education and care (West et al., 2014).

Kemethofer et al. (2022) highlight school leadership as a crucial determinant of instructional quality and pupil outcomes. Their research highlights the importance of theoretically robust leadership components, with multilevel structural equation modelling revealing group level effects on educational quality. Leithwood (2018) identifies school leadership as the second most influential factor in learner success, second only to teaching quality. However, studies from Ghana and Tanzania reveal challenges such as inadequate time allocation for Foundation Phase teachers and difficulties encountered by school principals in motivating teachers.

Effective pedagogical leaders empower teachers and promote a culture of continuous improvement (Gordon, 2019b). They prioritise professional development, resource provision, and collaborative planning (Harris, 2020b; Lloyd, 2020b). Mentorship and coaching are critical in supporting the professional growth of teachers, promoting a culture of peer mentoring and reflective practice (Gordon, 2019a; Talbot, 2019b). Establishing criteria for leadership development ensures that teachers receive the necessary support to meet evolving educational demands (ElAmin, 2023).

Quality in early childhood education is a multidimensional concept, subject to extensive debate among academics, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners (Wysłowska & Slot, 2020). High-quality ECCE programmes not only prepare children for formal schooling but also address social disadvantages and

segregation (Garvis & Taguchi, 2021). However, financial constraints and regulatory challenges persist in hindering progress.

Department of Education District officials play an instrumental role in supporting ECCE centres by providing guidance on curriculum, resources, and training (Smidts et al., 2018). Dahlberg and Moss (2020) advocate for a mentoring approach to foster collaboration and quality assurance rather than a monitoring centric stance. Effective leadership in ECCE transcends mere management; it encompasses vision, inspiration, and empowerment (Bush, 2020).

The South African Context

Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) in South Africa is deeply influenced by historical inequalities, socioeconomic challenges, and uneven policy application. The 2014 Early Childhood Development assessment conducted by the Department of Social Development highlighted poor-quality ECCE services in disadvantaged Black communities (RSA, DSD, 2015). Excell (2016) emphasises that government efforts to enhance ECCE provision in impoverished areas have been inadequate, further establishing disparities. Moreover, Garvis and Taguchi (2021) note that the effectiveness of interventions to improve ECCE quality varies significantly across countries, highlighting the need for tailored approaches in South Africa

Figure 1: Aerial photograph of a township adjacent to a suburban area in Cape Town, South Africa

Source: The Mail & Guardian Report by Katlego Mkwazi (2016).

The picture was taken by Johnny Miller who used a drone to take the aerial photographs that highlight the close proximity of poverty and wealth in the Western Cape, highlighting the enduring legacy of apartheid in South Africa led to the forced relocation of Coloured, Indian, and Black citizens under the Group Areas Act of 1950. They were prohibited from residing in central urban areas and were instead compelled to live in bleak and overcrowded township settlements on city outskirts, characterised by minimal access to educational resources (Smith, 2020). Against this backdrop, the present study examined stakeholders' perspectives comprising education department officials, teachers, and ECCE principals on pedagogical leadership and its relationship to the provision of quality ECCE in South African townships.

Research Method

Research Design

This study adopted a critical qualitative research approach to gain an in-depth understanding of ECCE stakeholders' perceptions of pedagogical leadership and its relationship to quality practices. Qualitative research, as described by Tilley (2019), allows for an exploration of specific areas of interest, providing valuable insights into educational policies and practices that may require revision. This approach involved gathering participants' perspectives and experiences through structured questioning (Sutton & Austin, 2015).

Selection of Participants

A purposive convenience sampling method was employed to select participants representing diverse perspectives within township ECCE settings. Convenience sampling facilitated accessible and in-depth data collection, while purposive sampling targeted individuals with specific expertise (Andrade, 2021; Firdaus et al., 2024). Participants were selected based on their experience in ECCE, ranging from 32 to 60 years of age, and included individuals with more than five years of professional experience. Due to the constraints of the Covid19 pandemic, only four of the seven potential participants contributed to the study. The subsequent paragraph provides an overview of the demographic details of the participants, with pseudonyms (P1 to P4) used to ensure confidentiality.

Demographic Details of Participants

Participant 1 (P1): A 54-year-old Grade R subject advisor who is a district official. With 14 years of experience, their focus lies in curriculum development and supporting teachers.

Participant 2 (P2): A 60-year-old principal, teacher, and owner of a community-based ECCE site. They have over 23 years of experience and hold a diploma in Early Childhood Development.

Participant 3 (P3): A 35-year-old Grade R teacher with 11 years of experience in a school-based setting. They are qualified with a Grade R Diploma in Education.

Participant 4 (P4): A 32-year-old teacher at an independent ECCE centre. Currently pursuing a master's degree, they have eight years of teaching experience.

Data Collection

Data was collected through semi structured interviews, which provided flexibility in probing participants' responses while maintaining a consistent structure across interviews (Wakelin et al., 2024). Each interview lasted approximately 60 to 65 minutes and was conducted via Microsoft Teams due to pandemic related restrictions. Participants provided consent for audio recordings, which were subsequently transcribed verbatim for analysis.

Data Analysis

Thematic analysis was utilised to identify patterns and themes in the data. Using ATLAS.ti software, the researchers systematically coded and categorised data according to Braun and Clarke's (2006) six phase methodology: familiarisation with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. This approach facilitated a comprehensive analysis of key themes related to pedagogical leadership and quality practices in ECCE.

Results and Discussion

Results

The study's findings were aligned with its aim, objectives, and research questions, highlighting participants' perspectives on pedagogical leadership and its influence on quality in ECCE. Thematic analysis revealed seven primary themes summarised below:

Themes Related to Participants' Views

1. Leaders' perception of pedagogical leadership and quality
2. The district official's role as a support structure and leader
3. Enacting quality in early childhood education
4. Belief that quality is important
5. Critical components of effective educational leadership
6. Criteria for quality
7. Improving the quality of instructional practice

Leaders' Perception of Pedagogical Leadership and Quality

Participants demonstrated a nuanced understanding of leadership and pedagogy, linking these concepts to motivation, decision making, and quality practices. Participant 1 described leadership as an action oriented and experimental process, while Participant 2 emphasised excellence in identifying and supporting learners with barriers to learning. These perspectives resonate with transformational leadership theories, which advocate for inspiring and guiding teams towards a shared vision (Bass & Avolio, 1994; Harsoyo, 2022).

Example of verbatim sayings:

Participant 1: Leadership is action, where the leader is a motivator who takes the lead, helps the team, and comes up with solutions that are inspiring and motivating.

Participant 2: Good Leadership is excellency in one's role. When doing things excellently, for example, when you teach in the class you identify learners with barriers and refer the child for support.

District Officials' Role as a Support Structure and Leader

The district official's role was identified as pivotal in providing guidance, resources, and monitoring support, although participants stressed the need for a mentoring, non-intimidating approach. Participant 2 highlighted the importance of prioritising support over criticism, aligning with collaborative leadership theories that emphasise shared responsibility and teamwork (Valdés & Sanhueza, 2023).

Example of verbatim saying:

Participant 2: Their role is more support, providing guidance on the curriculum, resources, training, and monitoring. Theirs is more to lead and show, not to criticise, and provide 80% support more than monitoring.

Participant 3: It's quite debatable. I agree with Participant 2. I used to be at the Government schools, and it would be frightening when expecting officials at your school.

Enacting Quality in Early Childhood Education

Participants unanimously agreed on the importance of quality in ECCE, highlighting the need for appropriate resources, effective communication with parents, and a well-structured curriculum. This aligns with Sylva et al.'s (2016) holistic framework, which advocates for enriched environments and consistent parent teacher engagement.

Example of verbatim saying: *Participant 4:* As a pedagogical leader, quality does matter to me as it guarantees success, produces good results, allows me to measure myself with the best in education, and is something that you need to maintain.

Participant 1: It determines the standards that I want in the ECD sites. It matters to me as a pedagogical leader because without quality in education, there will be no good learning programmes.

Critical components of effective educational leadership

Participants described the characteristics of effective educational leadership. Below are their verbatim responses:

Participant 2: To see that the teachers are teaching, including paying attention to every child in the learning programme, and to influence changes on how teachers are doing things; for example, having an open relationship with all role-players. To perform these teachers must possess the appropriate qualifications, training, experience, and be thoroughly versed with the curriculum and early years' policy. *Participant 1:* An effective leader is like a potter who should mould or shape the child. A dedicated practitioner who is well-qualified with a degree in early childhood education, and implements policy correctly, and is most likely to be successful in teaching young children by applying modern trends of teaching.

The participants felt that the indicators of quality educational leadership are reflected in the ability to attract the most qualified and experienced instructors to work in Government and private ECCE centres. Practitioners should possess a bachelor's degree in early years' education as a minimum requirement.

Additionally, they should demonstrate a strong commitment to effectively delivering the ECCE curriculum in accordance with the relevant educational policy, as well as demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of curriculum content and methodology.

Criteria for quality in early education leaders

Most participants referred to top management's performance as a criterion to rate quality in leadership, while some believed that ensuring quality at an ECCE institution is the personal responsibility of the educational leader who must ensure best practice by adhering to established standards and policy. This implies that leaders must provide ongoing support, suitable resources, and guidance to all children to achieve high-quality outputs. To improve leadership performance, it is important to satisfy certain quality criteria including collecting materials and preparing lessons in advance, identifying, and addressing specific areas of weakness in aspects of learning in the classroom, monitoring the progress of learners who are at risk, encouraging parental participation, and utilising and interpreting policies for guidance and implementation.

The findings confirmed that all participants agreed with the critical importance of quality in ECCE. This is valuable for leaders because it enables effective collaboration with other role-players towards achieving organisational goals and objectives. Since the participants were aware of the importance of quality leadership, they were queried about their understanding of what constituted quality in leadership. Their responses varied - some referred to performance standards and quality indicators. Generally, the results revealed that leaders were quite familiar with the concept of pedagogical leadership, but those who had worked in ECCE settings for a longer time were more knowledgeable about the aspect of quality in pedagogical leadership.

This aspect of quality in pedagogical leadership was revealed through participants' responses. Three of the participants (75% of the group) described quality as crucial for pedagogical leadership in ECCE. Another three participants (50% of the group) stated that quality is essential for maintaining an open relationship between teachers and the community, assisting teachers in implementing the curriculum, and improving their teaching plans. Three participants defined the educational benefit as a 'ship that sails miles' to build children. Four participants (100%) stated that quality is important for improving learner outcomes, teachers' delivery of lessons, and community involvement.

However, they did not specify why they believed this. Overall, the findings suggested that all participants were familiar with the importance of maintaining quality in ECCE.

Improve the quality of instructional practice.

The participants believed that the distinguishing characteristic of an educational leader is the ability to consistently perform at a high level, encouraging colleagues to improve their work ethic, and fostering positive relationships within the team in accordance with established quality performance standards. The importance of quality in educational leadership is reflected in several areas: ensuring academic success, achieving best practice, self-assessment of performance, adherence to specific standards, and the production and delivery of high-quality educational programmes. Additionally, quality promotes higher learning outcomes to raise the rate of academic performance, and to build a better future for all members of society to promote economic growth and reduce poverty through sound education practices.

Discussions

Based on the research data obtained, the discussion in this research provides valuable insights into the role of pedagogical leadership and the importance of quality in ECCE settings, aligning closely with the study's objectives theoretical framework and relevant literature.

Leaders' Perception of Pedagogical Leadership and Quality

Participants' understanding of leadership as an action-oriented, motivational role aligns with transformational leadership theories, which emphasise the importance of leaders inspiring and guiding their teams (Bass & Avolio, 1994). This correlation was evident in the participants' emphasis on decision-making, involvement, and excellence in leadership. Participant 4 views that "Leadership is action, where the leader is a motivator who takes the lead, helps the team, and comes up with solutions that are inspiring and motivating", this finding is consistent with previous research indicating that transformational leadership positively impacts educational outcomes by fostering a collaborative and motivated team environment (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

District Official's Role as a Support Structure and Leader

Participants highlighted the supportive role of District Officials, which aligns with theories of collaborative leadership. Effective collaboration and support from District Officials are crucial in fostering a positive school culture and improving

educational practices (Harris & Spillane, 2008). While participant 2 view that pedagogical role of leaders is more of support, providing guidance on the curriculum, resources, training, and monitoring, she emphasised the need for more to lead and show, not to criticise, and provided 80% support more than monitoring. This perspective is supported by existing literature, which highlights that supportive district leadership enhances school leaders' capacities to implement curriculum and instructional improvements (Honig, 2012).

Enacting Quality in Early Childhood Education: Quality in ECCE was unanimously deemed critical, with participants emphasising the need for appropriate materials, resources, and effective communication with parents. This theme aligns with the literature that stresses the importance of a well-resourced and communicative educational environment in fostering quality early childhood education (Sylva et al., 2004). Research by Epstein (2001) also supports this finding, highlighting the significance of family and community partnerships in promoting educational quality.

Belief in the Importance of Quality

Participants highlighted the importance of leadership awareness of individual needs and societal influences, which is crucial for effective pedagogical leadership. This aligns with Bronfenbrenner's ecological systems theory, which emphasises the impact of various environmental systems on child development (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Here is what participant 4 said: "As a pedagogical leader, quality matters to me as it guarantees success and produces good results." This participant viewpoint is reinforced by studies that show quality leadership significantly influences educational outcomes and institutional success (Hallinger & Heck, 1998).

Critical Components of Effective Educational Leadership: Participants described effective educational leadership as involving various attributes, including qualifications, experience, and an understanding of the curriculum. This aligns with the theoretical premise that effective leadership promotes a positive organisational climate and facilitates the achievement of institutional goals (Roy & Pradhan, 2022).

Participant 2: "To see that the teachers are teaching and paying attention to every child, influencing change in how teachers do things." *Participant 1:* "An effective leader is like a potter who should mold or shape the child." This finding is consistent with research by Day et al. (2009), which identifies the critical role of educational leadership in shaping school performance and student outcomes.

Criteria for Quality in Early Education Leader

Participants noted that leadership quality is often measured by performance standards and the ability to provide support and resources. This perspective aligns with previous studies indicating that clear criteria and standards are essential for assessing and ensuring quality in educational leadership (Robinson, Lloyd, & Rowe, 2008). 'Quality' according to participant 4 ...determines the standards she wants in the ECD sites and matters because without it, there will be no good learning programs.

Improving the Quality of Instructional Practice: Participants believed that fostering a culture of continuous improvement and high performance is a key aspect of leadership. This finding is supported by research showing that ongoing professional development and a commitment to best practices lead to improved educational outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2000).

The findings suggest several policy implications

Inclusion of Performance Standards: Policy should include performance standards to ensure quality teaching and learning in ECCE settings. This recommendation is supported by literature emphasizing the importance of standards in achieving educational quality (Marsh, 2000).

Support and Oversight by District Officials: District Officials should provide support and oversight at ECCE centers to ensure quality pedagogical leadership practices. This aligns with research indicating that supportive oversight enhances school performance (Honig, 2012).

Adherence to DBE Prescribed Standards: Stakeholders should embrace the Department of Basic Education's prescribed quality standards, such as those in the Norms and Standards Policy, to enhance outcomes (Department of Basic Education, 2020).

Understanding Stakeholders' Perceptions - Leadership should understand stakeholders' perceptions of quality to promote better community engagement and enhance the holistic growth of children. This is consistent with Epstein's (2001) findings on the importance of community engagement in education.

Perception Influence on Leaders' Participation - The study found a positive correlation between educational leaders' perceptions of quality and their commitment to implementing quality standards. Leaders with a better understanding of quality performed better, accentuating the importance of

aligning leaders' perceptions with the aims of quality assurance (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Engagement Influence on Quality Implementation - Proactive and committed engagement of educational leaders is crucial for fostering quality implementation. This aligns with research indicating that engaged and motivated leaders are essential for driving educational improvements (Fullan, 2001).

Recommendations

The findings emphasise the critical role of pedagogical leadership in fostering quality in ECCE. The recommendations include the following:

Investing in Leadership Development - Policymakers should prioritise professional development programmes to equip ECCE leaders with the skills necessary for quality improvement.

Enhancing Collaborative Practices - Fostering teamwork between stakeholders, including teachers, parents, and district officials, is essential for creating supportive and effective educational environments.

Implementing Performance Standards - Clear criteria for assessing leadership quality should be established to guide leaders in their roles.

Increasing Resource Allocation - Adequate resources and support structures must be provided to ensure the delivery of high-quality ECCE programmes.

Conclusion

This study highlights the important role of pedagogical leadership in advancing the quality of early childhood education, emphasising the need for strategic investments in leadership development and stakeholder collaboration. By fostering strong partnerships among policymakers, ECCE leaders, teachers, and district officials, high-quality ECCE environments can be cultivated to support the holistic growth and development of all children. The findings reaffirm the transformative potential of effective and informed leadership in addressing systemic challenges, promoting equity, and driving sustained improvements in early childhood education. However, the study's limitations, including constraints associated with virtual data collection and a small sample size, highlight the need for further research. Future investigations should examine the long-term impacts of leadership training programmes and consider the influence of contextual factors, such as socio-economic disparities, on ECCE practices to deepen understanding and inform more effective interventions.

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